

The Political Environment in the Global Innovation Index

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The "Political environment" variable in the Global Innovation Index (GII) measures the quality and stability of a country's political context, which is a crucial factor in its ability to promote and sustain innovation. This variable evaluates several aspects related to governance, including political stability, the quality of institutions, the presence of corruption, and the protection of fundamental rights such as freedom of expression and association. Political stability is essential because a stable environment reduces risks for businesses and investors, fostering a climate of trust necessary for the development of innovative activities. When a country experiences political instability, internal conflicts, or frequent government changes, it becomes more difficult to attract investments in research and development, as uncertainty discourages long-term investments. Another aspect assessed is the quality of institutions, which refers to the government's ability to formulate and implement effective policies. Countries with strong institutions can support economic growth and encourage innovation through clear, transparent, and predictable laws and regulations. Conversely, weak or inefficient institutions can hinder innovation by creating bureaucratic obstacles or failing to provide adequate intellectual property protection systems. Finally, the presence of corruption and the respect for fundamental rights significantly impact the political environment. Corruption undermines trust in the political and institutional system, while a lack of respect for human rights can limit citizens' participation in the country's economic and social life, hampering the development of an innovative environment. In summary, a favorable and stable political environment is crucial for creating ideal conditions for innovation, as it promotes trust, predictability, and institutional efficiency. The data refers to the period between 2013 and 2022.

The Political Environment in 2022. The data on the political environment in the 2022 Global Innovation Index (GII) provides a clear indication of how political stability and governance quality influence a country's ability to foster innovation and attract investments. A stable political environment, characterized by good governance and transparency, is essential for creating an ecosystem that supports innovation, economic progress, and technological development. At the top of the rankings is Singapore, which, with a perfect score of 100, confirms itself as the country with the most favorable political environment. Its excellence in this area reflects extremely stable political institutions and an efficient administration capable of promoting a predictable and secure regulatory environment for businesses. Singapore is followed by Nordic countries such as Denmark (90.7), Norway (90.3), and New Zealand (90.2). The ranking highlights how countries with well-established and transparent democratic systems tend to achieve the highest scores. These nations, known for their political and institutional stability, are able to create an environment of trust, essential for developing innovative projects and attracting international talent and capital. Switzerland (89.3), Finland (88.6), and Luxembourg (90.1) represent European examples of excellence, confirming the importance of solid governance and a stable political framework in promoting innovation. Their top positions are closely linked to these countries' ability to provide well-regulated political systems with low corruption and strong respect for the rule of law. In the mid-range, we find countries such as the United States (78.2), the United Kingdom (77), and France (76.5). Although these countries maintain a degree of political stability, their scores reflect some political uncertainties in recent years. For the

United States, growing political polarization and frequent changes in public policies may have negatively impacted the perception of its political environment. The United Kingdom is still dealing with the consequences of Brexit, which has created uncertainties on both political and economic fronts, affecting its GII score. Among emerging countries, Vietnam (65.2) and Rwanda (66.7) stand out, both considered successful examples of improving their political governance. Their progress reflects political reforms aimed at strengthening institutions, reducing corruption, and creating a more favorable environment for business and innovation. However, despite these advances, these countries still face significant challenges to achieving levels of political stability comparable to those at the top of the rankings. On the opposite end of the spectrum, countries such as Iraq (23.3), Mali (33.3), and Myanmar (35.9) face serious problems of political instability. In these countries, internal conflicts, widespread corruption, and weak governments severely limit their ability to attract investments and create a favorable environment for innovation. The severe political instability in these regions not only impedes economic growth but also hinders the development of the infrastructure and institutions necessary to support technological advancement. In conclusion, the analysis of the political environment in the 2022 GII highlights the crucial importance of stable and transparent governance in fostering innovation. Countries with high levels of political stability enjoy greater investor confidence, better access to capital, and a stronger ability to promote innovation, while those with lower performance face complex challenges that hinder their economic and technological development.

The Political Environment Between 2013 and 2022. The data on the political environment in the Global Innovation Index between 2013 and 2022 shows a variety of trends across the examined countries, with some experiencing significant improvements and others seeing a decrease in their political stability and governance quality. One of the most notable findings concerns the improvement in countries that have traditionally faced significant political challenges. Pakistan, for example, saw a 118.06% increase, rising from a score of 21.6 to 47.1, thanks to institutional reforms and greater consolidation of political stability. This change can be attributed to policies that improved security and governance, although problems with corruption and internal conflicts remain. Similarly, China experienced a remarkable growth (+71.68%), increasing from 39.2 to 67.3, demonstrating its ability to maintain relative political stability despite external geopolitical pressures and internal tensions. Vietnam improved its political environment with a 51.28% increase, thanks to political reforms that strengthened governance and stability, attracting foreign investments and stimulating innovation. African countries like Côte d'Ivoire (+48.88%) and Rwanda (+33.67%) also benefited from an improvement in political stability, aided by post-conflict pacification and reforms that enhanced the quality of institutions. These advances show how political reforms and better governance can create a more favorable environment for economic development and innovation. On the other hand, several countries experienced a significant reduction in political stability between 2013 and 2022. Mali, for instance, saw a dramatic decrease of 25.67%, reflecting severe instability caused by internal conflicts and government changes. Mozambique also registered a 21.03% decline, due to security issues, political instability, and economic challenges. This decline reflects the difficult context many African countries face, with fragile governments and conflicts undermining stability and the ability to promote innovation. Some developed countries also saw a decline in political stability. Finland lost 9.5%, and Germany experienced a 6.29% drop. These reductions may be linked to increasing political polarization and global economic uncertainty, which have put pressure even on established democracies. Furthermore, the United Kingdom saw a 3.39% decrease, likely influenced by the political turmoil related to Brexit, which created uncertainties on both political and institutional fronts. Scandinavian countries and others traditionally considered stable, such as Norway (-3.01%) and Denmark (-4.22%), experienced slight declines, reflecting a rise in political volatility even in

historically solid environments. These countries now face new challenges, including internal and global political pressures, which could affect their ability to maintain a favorable political environment. Overall, the data shows that political stability is a dynamic and complex factor, influenced by both internal and external elements. Countries that have implemented significant political reforms have seen improvements in their stability, while those involved in conflicts or facing internal political crises have experienced significant declines. The political environment is a crucial aspect for attracting investments and stimulating innovation, and its fluctuation has a direct impact on economic development.

Conclusions. The value of the political environment has, on average, increased between 2013 and 2022, rising from 60.11 to 62.57, representing a growth of 4.08%. The top performers are: Pakistan with +118.06%, China with +71.68%, Vietnam with +51.28%, Côte d'Ivoire with +48.88%, and Azerbaijan with +44.8%. The worst performers are: Burkina Faso with -15.49%, Tanzania with -17.38%, Zambia with -19.54%, Mozambique with -21.03%, and Mali with -25.67%.

Performance	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performance	Pakistan	21,6	47,1	25,5	118,06
	China	39,2	67,3	28,1	71,68
	Vietnam	43,1	65,2	22,1	51,28
	Cote d'Ivoire	35,8	53,3	17,5	48,88
	Azerbaijan	40,4	58,5	18,1	44,8
Worse Performance	Burkina Faso	51	43,1	-7,9	-15,49
	Tanzania	54,1	44,7	-9,4	-17,38
	Zambia	56,8	45,7	-11,1	-19,54
	Mozambique	56,1	44,3	-11,8	-21,03
	Mali	44,8	33,3	-11,5	-25,67

Source: Global Innovation Index

Link: <https://prosperitydata360.worldbank.org/en/indicator/WIPO+GII+8>

